

FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ASSESSMENT

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Abstract: This article briefly describes the factors affecting students' academic achievement. It is highlighted that bringing students' learning to a high quality level is an important task facing the national education system, as well as a number of current problems and shortcomings that have a negative impact on academic learning.

Keywords: education, student, academic mastering, advanced technologies, science, material and technical base, reforms, psychological mechanism.

To raise the academic mastery of students to a new level in the fields of youth and pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology on a global scale, to develop theoretical and practical, innovative, creative, compositional, critical, technical and visual thinking in them, the influence of educational resources, the importance of information technology, the culture of thinking. many studies are being conducted on the problems of formation, development of scientific thinking through learning foreign languages. In this direction, great attention is being paid to the problem of identifying and introducing psychological mechanisms that represent priority methods and conditions for raising students' learning to a new level of quality, and opportunities are being created to study it as a topical issue in this field.

During the years of independence in our country, special attention has been paid to the issue of creating the necessary opportunities for the realization of the intellectual potential of young people. In particular, in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 - educating young people who are physically healthy, spiritually and mentally developed, independent-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, with a firm outlook on life, deepening democratic reforms and increasing their social activity in the process of developing civil society tasks are defined. As part of the measures implemented today, it is important to carry out scientific research works on the improvement of the psychological mechanisms of the development of thinking that ensures the increase of the activity of students in the educational process, the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for professional activity, and the independent and creative approach to work on problems.

In order to improve the academic performance of students, first of all, it is necessary to eliminate or reduce to a minimum level the shortcomings that arise

in the educational system, to organize the educational process in accordance with the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of students, to make extensive use of advanced technologies, to apply the latest achievements of science, to make students active participants in the educational process, to make them the most it will be necessary to provide modern didactic tools.

The world who conducted effective research in this field (Dj. Cattell, Ch. Spearman, B.G. Ananiev, A.N. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinshtein, G.S. Abramova, C. Vygotsky, V.V. Davydov, A .N. Leontiev, S.L. Aleksandrov, N.S. Kuzmina, T.V. Markova. , V.D. Shadrikov) and Uzbek scientists (M.G. Davletshin, E.G'. Goziev, B.R. Kadirov, G'.B. Shoumarov, V.M. Karimova, A.M. Jabborov, D.G .Mukhamedova, A.I.Rasulov) determined that many factors affect the learning and success of students studying in educational institutions. These factors can be divided into the following groups: material and economic (financial) status, health, age, family status, level of scientific training before school and university, goal-oriented organization of one's activities, planning of future dreams and goals, and having control skills (first of all, education), the reasons for choosing a higher education institution (specialty), the adequacy of initial ideas about the characteristics of university education, the form of education (day, evening, part-time, distance education, etc.), the availability and amount of tuition fees, the educational process at the university organization, the material and technical base of the university, the level of qualifications of teachers and employees, the reputation of the university, and most importantly, the individual psychological characteristics of students.

Students studying in higher education institutions can be divided into two groups: the first group - those who study continuously to acquire knowledge and professional skills, work with will, overcome various difficulties that arise only through their intelligence, strength and desire to achieve goals, the second group - are those who do everything under pressure, fail to master, and face difficulties in solving the problems that arise in the educational system.

Students can be divided into many types, taking into account their value system, differences in it, level of personal maturity, focus on specific education, successful learning. As a basis for distinguishing these typologies, the relationship to the profession, study, science and life values of students and the whole system is shown.

Russian scientist L.D. Stolyarenko divides students into three types according to their nature and behavior patterns.

The interests of the first type of students go beyond the limits of knowledge indicated in the curriculum and programs of the subjects. They actively participate in all aspects of university life and are directed to a wide specialization and multifaceted professional training.

The second type is characterized by a clear focus on narrow specialization. Here too, students' cognitive activity goes beyond the scope of educational programs, it is directed only within the framework of their professional field.

Cognitive activity in the third type of students is aimed at mastering knowledge and skills within the curriculum. These students show a minimum level of activity and creativity in the educational process.

According to the study guide created under the leadership of M.V. Bulanova-Toporkova, students are divided into five groups according to the mastery level:

1. Active students in all aspects of the learning process. Due to their hard work and diligence, they demonstrate excellent academic success.

2. The students of the second group are also active in all directions of educational activities, but they do not pay attention to getting deep knowledge, they study based on the principle of "even if little is good".

3. Students of the third group limit their activities in a narrow professional sphere, they try to selectively acquire only knowledge necessary for future professional activities. They study special subjects well, but do not pay enough attention to non-specialized subjects.

4. Students in the fourth group are interested only in subjects they like and are easy to teach. They often skip classes, ignoring some subjects almost completely.

5. The fifth group includes "lazy students" who are not interested in any field of knowledge. As a rule, they study at higher educational institutions "at someone's request", at the request of their parents. The goal of students in this group is to study and become mature specialists in their field. rather than gaining a "diploma" due to external influence.

Raising student learning in Uzbekistan to a higher level is one of the most important tasks facing the national education system. Because intellectual development and professional preparation of students directly depends on their level of academic mastery. At the same time, the fact that a number of current problems and shortcomings that negatively affect students' academic learning remain, and that the scale of systematic work aimed at eliminating them is small, worries many people.

Current qualification requirements in educational institutions, curricula and programs should be focused on the formation of practical skills in graduates in terms of content, reducing the share of non-specialist subjects in the curricula, forming students' skills of critical thinking, independent search and analysis of information, effective organization of practical training in production enterprises, for professionals in training to create a labor market based on modern requirements, to train professors and teachers in higher educational institutions according to modern educational requirements, to provide them with sufficient material and technical base and information resources, to introduce transparent mechanisms for conducting science Olympiads in higher education institutions and to systematically establish work with Olympiad winners, higher It is possible to achieve positive results in higher education by strengthening the spiritual and moral content in education, educating young people in the spirit of patriotism based on respect for national values, humanitarianism and high spiritual ideals, and strengthening their immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies.

In order to improve the academic performance of students, first of all, it is necessary to eliminate or minimize the above-mentioned shortcomings, to organize the educational process in accordance with the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of students, to make extensive use of advanced technologies, to apply the latest achievements of science, to make students active participants in the educational process, to make them the most modern. it will be necessary to provide didactic tools

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